

Legal Rights of Women in Health and Safety – Conceptual

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Abstract

The social and human rights of women is the legal rights of women. During the 17th and 18th century had more negative than positive affects on women’s rights in the Indian subcontinent. These problem includes female infanticide, and improve age of consent, scholars agree that overall women’s legal rights and freedoms were restricted during this period. The use of Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques such as ultrasound for the purpose of Detecting genetic abnormalities, and to prevent misuse of such techniques for sex determination, which leads to the elimination of the female fetus. Certain traditional practices, such as female genital mutilation, also affect women’s health. Worldwide, young women and adolescent girls are the populations most affected by HIV/AIDS. Reproductive rights are understood as the rights of both men and women but are most frequently advanced by women’s rights. Medical termination of pregnancy (MTP) act 1971, lays down the conditions under which a pregnancy can be terminate the person or persons who can perform and the place where can be pregnancy can be terminated by MTP act 1971.

Keywords: Legal rights of women, Health, Women’s health, Reproductive rights, Abortion, Forced pregnancy, Regulation and Prevention of Misuse, Section-3.4.5.6. 16.16A. 17.17A.18 22.23 Clause-2.3.4.

Introduction

Indians used their Hindu legal code as a basis for their rights and customs. MANU SMRITI protected women’s property rights as well as rights to inheritance. But it is also insisted that women are placed under a male guardianship at all times such as father from birth, husband in marriage and sons as a widow. The PANCHAYATS, which composed mostly male village elders but, these excluded not were always by women. This system fared women better than the normative Hindu code, but the normative Hindu code better than women by the colonial Anglo-Indian judiciary.

Definition

The legal rights of women is the social and human rights of women

Health is defined according to the World Health Organization said as “a state of complete physical, mental, social spiritual and vocational well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity” –WHO (1948), **Women’s health refers to the health of women,**

Reproductive rights are often defined to include freedom from female genital mutilation [FGM], and forced abortion and forced sterilization.

Abortion

According to Human Rights Watch, “Abortion is a highly emotional subject and one that excites deeply held opinions. However, equitable access to safe abortion services is, first and foremost, a human right.

Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Regulation and Prevention of Misuse) ACT 1994,

India has a 48.20% female population compare to 51.80% male population. India has 49,314,062 more males population than the females’ population. India is in the 191st position out of 201 countries in terms of female to male ratio. Among Asian countries, India is at 43rd position out of 51.

As per Census 2011, the Gender ratio of India is 943 females per 1000 males. In rural areas, there are 949 females to 1000 men, while in an urban area ,there are 929 females to 1000 males. Rural India has 21,813,264 more males, and urban India has 13,872,275 more males than females. India’s Sex Ratio had increased by number 10 from 933 in 2001 to 943 in 2011. In rural and urban India, the Sex ratio has improved by number 3 and 29, respectively. In 1901, India had the highest sex ratio of 972.

As of 2020, below 65-69 age groups, India had more males than females. Below 24 year population, there are 11 more males per 100 females. The female population is almost double above 100 years. Among states, Kerala has the highest sex ratio of 1084 females to 1000 males.

The Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Regulation and Prevention of Misuse) Amendment Act 2002, came into force with effect from 14th February 2003. PNDT Act 1994 now stands renamed as “The Pre-Conception and Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Prohibition of sex Selection) Act”. The Act provides for the prohibition of sex selection, before or after conception.

Purpose

- Detecting genetic abnormalities or
- Sex-linked disorders in the fetus.
- To prevent misuse of such techniques for sex determination which lead to the elimination of the female fetus

The Main Provisions of the PNDT Act are as follows

Section-3

1. Only registered Genetic Centers, Laboratory, or Clinics can carry out prenatal diagnostic tests.
2. The only medical person who possesses the medical qualification prescribed in the Act can conduct the test (Sonologist)
3. Only in the place registered under this Act.
4. Scanner or any other equipment capable of detecting the sex of the fetus to any counseling center. Laboratory or person not registered under the Act.

Section-4 Clause-3

Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques shall be used the following conditions:

1. The Age of the pregnant woman is above 35 years
2. The pregnant woman has undergone two or more spontaneous abortions or fetal loss.
3. Exposed to drugs, radiation, chemicals or infection by the pregnant woman.

Section-4 Clause-4

No person, including a relative or husband of the pregnant woman, shall seek or encourage to conduct of any Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques on her except for the purpose specified in Clause 2.

Section-5

The person carrying out PNDT has to obtain the informed consent of the woman in the prescribed form and language she understands. She must be made aware of the possible side effects. An undertaking is also required from the woman, and she will not terminate the pregnancy if there is a normal child of either sex.

Section-5 Clause-2

No person, including the person conducting [PNDT,] shall communicate to the pregnant woman concerned or her relatives or any other person the sex of the fetus by words, signs, or in any other manner.

Section-6

No person shall, by whatever means, causes or allow to be caused selection of sex before or after conception.

Section-16

The function of the State Board:

1. To advise the Central Government on policy matters relating to the use of pre-natal diagnostic techniques, sex selection techniques, and against their misuse.
2. To review and monitor implementation of the Act and recommended to the Central Government changes in the said Act and Rules.
3. To create public awareness against the practice of pre-conception sex selection and pre-natal determination of sex of fetal, leading to female feticide.
4. To oversee the performance of various bodies constituted under the Act and take appropriate steps to ensure its proper and effective implementation.

Section-16 A

Functions of the State Supervising Board:

1. To create public awareness against the practice of pre-conception sex selection and pre-natal determination of sex of fetus, leading to female feticide in the State.
2. To review the activities of the Appropriate Authorities functioning in the State and recommend appropriate action on Violation of the Act.
3. To monitor implementation of provisions of the Act and the Rules and make suitable recommendations relating to it, to the Board.
4. To send such consolidated reports as may be prescribed in respect of various activities undertaken in the State under the Act to the Board the Central Government.

Section-17

Members of the Appropriate Authority:

1. An officer of or above the rank of the Joint Director of Health and Family Welfare Chairperson.
2. The woman representing Woman's organization: and

Functions of the appropriate authority

1. To grant registration or cancel registrations.
2. To take appropriate legal action against the use of any sex selection technique by any person at any place, sue-motto, or brought to its notice and also to initiate independent investigations in such matter.
3. To create public awareness against the practice of sex selection or pre-natal determination of sex.
4. To supervise the implementation of the provisions of the Act and Rules.
5. To recommend to the Central Board and State Boards modifications required in the rules by changes in technology or social conditions.
6. To take action on the recommendations of the Advisory Committee made after investigation of a complaint about suspension or cancellation of registration.

Section-17 A

Powers of Appropriate Authority:

1. Summoning of any person who has any information relating to the violation of the provisions of this Act or the Rules made there under.
2. Production of any document or materials or object relating to clause (a).
3. Issuing search warrant for any place suspected to be indulging in sex selection techniques or pre-natal sex determination.

Section-18

No person shall open the Genetic Counseling Center Laboratory Clinic having ultrasound or scanner or render services or any of them unless such Center/laboratory/Clinic is duly registered by the Act.

Section-22

1. No person/ organization/ genetic counseling center/ laboratory/ clinic having an ultrasound machine/ scanner capable of undertaking the determination of sex of fetus shall issue, publish any advertisement in any form before conception available at such center.
2. Any person who contravenes the provisions of this section shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to three years and with fine which may extend to Rs.10,000/-.

Section-23

1. If charges are framed against the Medical Practitioner, his/her registration in the Medical Council will be Suspended till the case is disposed of, and on conviction, his/her name will be removed for 5 years for the first offense and permanently for the subsequent offense.
2. Any person who seeks the help of Genetic Counseling Center/Clinic/laboratory for sex selection he/she shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to 3 years and with fine which may extend to Rs.50,000/- for the first offense and for any subsequent offense with imprisonment which may extend to 5 years and with fine which may extend to Rs.1,00,000/-.

Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971

Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP) Act, 1971 lies down

1. The conditions under which a pregnancy can be terminated.
2. The person or persons who can perform.
3. The place where pregnancy can be terminated under MTP act 1971.

The Following Conditions

Medical: Where continuation of the pregnancy might endanger the mother's life or cause grave injury to her physical or mental health.

1. Eugenic: Where there is a substantial risk of the child being born with handicaps due to physical or mental abnormalities.
2. Humanitarian: Where pregnancy is the result of rape.
3. Socio-economic: Where actual or reasonably foreseeable environments could lead to the risk of injury to the health of the mother.
4. Failure of contraceptive devices: The anguish caused by an unwanted pregnancy resulting from the failure of any contraceptive device or method can be presumed to constitute a grave mental injury to the health of the mother. This condition is a unique feature of the Indian Law and virtually allows abortion on request, given the difficulty of proving that the pregnancy was not caused by the failure of contraception.

The written consent of the guardian is necessary before performing an abortion in women under 18 years of age, and in lunatics, even if they are older than 18 years.

The Person(s) who can Perform Abortion

The Act provides Medical Practitioners having experience in gynecology and obstetrics to perform abortions where the length of pregnancy does not exceed 12 weeks. However, where the pregnancy exceeds 12 weeks and is not necessary to terminate the pregnancy.

Where abortion can be done, the Act stipulates that no termination of pregnancy shall be made at any place other than a hospital established or maintained by the Government or approved for this Act by the Government.

Abortion services are provided in strict confidence by hospitals. The name of the abortion seeker is kept confidential since abortion has been treated as a statutory personal matter.

MTP Rules (1975): Rules and Regulations framed initially were altered in October 1975 to eliminate time-consuming procedures involved in MTP and to make services more readily available. These changes have occurred in 3 administrative areas.

Approval by Board

Under the new rules, the Chief Medical Officer of the district is empowered to certify that a doctor has the necessary training in gynecology to Certification Boards was removed.

Qualification to Perform Abortion

The new rules allow for registered medical practitioners to qualify through on the spot training:

“If he has assisted an RMP in the performance of 25 cases of medical termination of pregnancy in an approved institution”,

The doctor may also qualify to do MTO's under the new rules if he has one or more of the following qualifications which are similar to the old rules:

1. Six-month horsemanship in obstetrics and gynecology (OBG)
2. A post-graduate in OBG
3. Three years of practice in OBG for those doctors registered by MTP Act 1971.
4. One year of practice in OBG for those doctors registered on or after the date of commencement of the Act.

The Place where Abortion is Performed

Under the new rules, non-government institutions may also take up abortions provided they obtain a license from the Chief Medical Officer of the district, this eliminating the requirement of private clinics obtaining a Board License.

Conclusion

Different scientific techniques such as amniocenteses and sonography were created to detect genetic disorders in the fetus. But these techniques were supported to be used mainly to detect the genetic deformities at the Pre-Natal stage and have become very popular for the detection of the sex of a fetus and elimination of female fetus through abortions. These above act emphasis on to create awareness about health and safety among the women and know the rights of women in our country

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